

INVESTIGATING THE FLEXURAL PROPERTIES OF BAMBOO FIBRE – PP COMPOSITES CONSOLIDATED UNDER INERT ATMOSPHERE

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1. Introduction

Bamboo *Guadua Angustifolia* is one of the 3 largest bamboo species in the world and is the most important tropical bamboo in America due to its large size, excellent properties and natural durability [1]. Among other well-known natural fibres, bamboo fibres have been well recognized because of their good specific properties and they are often called “natural glass fibres” [2]. Recently high quality long bamboo fibres have been used as a reinforcement in epoxy matrices with good results [3].

The overall advantages of bamboo fibres have not yet been fully exploited for high-tech thermoplastic composite applications because they are still limited to fairly low melting temperature thermoplastic matrices (e.g. polypropylene). See Table 1.

One of the reasons is because of the natural fibres’ thermal stability, where the first levels of degradation occur typically at temperatures above 180°C in detriment to the mechanical properties of the fibre [4]. High temperatures are applied mainly during the manufacturing (e.g. compression molding) where the thermoplastic matrix needs to have reduced viscosity enabling the impregnation of the fibre bundles and the shaping of the part.

In order to reduce thermal degradation, an inert atmosphere during the composite consolidation phase could present a potential solution. Experiments with single natural fibres have been carried out in a nitrogen atmosphere with remarkable results [5].

Apart for single fibre studies, only a few studies have been done to observe the effect of manufacturing natural fibre composites under inert atmosphere on the mechanical properties.

Thermoplastic	Melting temperature (°C)	Shaping Temperature (°C)
PolyEthylene (PE)	120-145	150-200
PolyPropylene (PP)	165	185-200
PolyVinylidene Fluoride (PVDF)	170	190-230
PoyAmide 6 (PA6)	220	240
PolyButylene Terephthalate (PBT)	225	250-280
PolyEthylene Terephthalate (PET)	255	280-300
PolyEtherEtheKetone (PEEK)	343	365-380

Table 1. Melting and shaping temperature for commonly used thermoplastics [6].

In this study, with the aim to characterize and to quantify the effect of thermal degradation on mechanical properties during the manufacturing process, single bamboo fibres and bamboo fibre – polypropylene composites (BFPC) were produced at different (relatively) high temperatures in different environments.

2. Methodology

2.1 Materials

Bamboo culms (*Guadua angustifolia*) were extracted from a typical bamboo plantation in Colombia, specifically from the Coffee Region, at 1.300 meters above sea level. Technical fibres were extracted from the bamboo culms using a purely mechanical extraction process that neither uses chemicals nor high temperature (see Fig. 1). The length of the extracted fibres is the internode length, which for 48 month old culms is reported to be between 20 and 35 cm. The fibre diameter ranged between 90 and 280 μm . The polypropylene (PP) film with a density of 0.9 g/cm^3 and 20 μm thickness was supplied by Propex GmbH (Germany).

Fig.1. Extracted bamboo fibres

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Thermal treatment for single fibres

The characterization of the thermal degradation in single bamboo fibres was carried out by measuring their tensile strength and stiffness behaviour after thermal treatment, at different temperature-time couples in air and inert environments. Table 2 shows the different combinations of temperature and

exposure time for the fibres. The starting temperature was 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (time = 0) and then the material was heated at a heating rate 5 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ until the target temperature and then kept constant until the desired time. Before and after the thermal treatment, the fibres were conditioned at room temperature and 50% relative humidity for 48 hours.

Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Time (min)					
	50	60	70	80	100	120
180		■				■
200	■		■		■	■
220		■	■	■		
250	■	■				

Table 2. Temperature-time couples for thermal treatment of single bamboo fibres.

2.2.2 Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) for bamboo fibres and PP samples were carried out on a SDT (Simultaneous DSC and TGA) Q600 T.A. instrument. The experiments were carried out under air and inert atmosphere at a flow rate of 20mL/min and a heating rate of 5 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. Samples between 21 and 26 mg were used. For the analysis of the information, TA Universal Analysis software was used.

2.2.3 Single fibre test set-up

The method to determine the individual cross sectional area for each individual tested fibre, comprises of weighing the fibres and then dividing the weight by the fibre length and apparent density (1,4 gr/cm^3 [3]). A diameter can be estimated assuming that the fibres have a constant cross-section.

The single fibre tensile test was carried out using a mini-Instron 5943 at the Department of Metallurgy and Materials Engineering, KU Leuven (Belgium) under standard environmental conditions (21 $^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 50 ± 2 %RH). The fibres were pneumatically

clamped at 5 bar of pressure using rubber-faced clamps of 10x30 mm. These clamps allowed reducing fibre manipulations and avoiding the use of a paper frame. A vertical visual reference was used during placement of the samples on the grips in order to avoid fibre misalignment. The latter can lead to bending stresses at the grips, and thus cause premature failure. The crosshead speed was 0.85 mm/min with a 1kN load cell. The load was registered during the entire test. The gauge length used to determine the strength of the fibre was 30 mm. The number of fibres for each batch was at least 20 successful test samples.

The fibre Young's modulus was determined from the slope of the stress-strain curve (between 0.1 and 0.3% of deformation) of single fibres tested at 70 mm span length. With this "long" span length, the machine compliance (i.e. slippage on the grips) becomes negligible, giving an accurate measurement of the elongation of the samples during the test, and thus, a reliable calculation for the Young's modulus.

In order to corroborate the reliability of this methodology, the Young's modulus obtained from untreated fibres tested at several span lengths (40, 50 and 70 mm) was compared with the values obtained by Osorio *et al* [3], for the same fibres. The results showed that fibres tested at "long" span lengths (i.e. 70 mm) did not present a significant difference with the reference material. Both studies were performed on the same type of bamboo fibres and under the same conditions. In Osorio's study [3], a theoretical correction for the machine compliance, developed by Defoirdt *et al* [7], was applied in order to determine the real elongation of the specimens. This methodology consisted of plotting the modulus versus 1/span length. The extrapolation to 1/span = 0 (infinite fibre length), provides the material modulus for which slip and machine compliance may be ignored. When thus the real material modulus is known, an estimation can be made for the machine compliance. Knowing this compliance, strain values can be corrected (this calculation must be done for every single experiment).

2.2.4 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) observations

Micrographs of fibres and composites were made by scanning electron microscopy (SEM30 XL FEG). The samples were sputter coated with gold for further observations, using secondary electrons and with a beam voltage between 10 and 15 kV.

2.2.5 Composite production

Thermoplastic composites were prepared by compression moulding of stacks (~6 layers) of bamboo uni-directional preforms inserted in between the polypropylene (PP) films. The bamboo fibre preforms were dried overnight at 65 °C to prevent problems due to moisture. Fibre volume fraction was set around 45% by weight measurements. Several temperatures were used for the consolidation of the composites (175, 185, 200, 220 and 230 °C) in air environment, following the temperature profile shown in Fig. 2. In this procedure and starting at RT, the heating rate was 5 °C/min followed by a preheating stage during 5 minutes (20 °C lower than the target temperature). Then, the temperature was increased again at the same rate until the target temperature, for another 5 minutes. After this, the mould started to be cooling down. A constant pressure of 15 bars was used during all process.

Fig. 2. Temperature profile used in compression moulding for the elaboration of bamboo fibre-PP composites (BFPC).

A similar temperature profile (Fig. 2.) was followed for the BFPC consolidated in inert environment at

200 °C, 220 °C and 230 °C. A schematic view of the bagging system in order to maintain a controlled atmosphere (argon) around the mould during the forming phase, is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Schematic representation of the set-up for the production of bamboo fibre-PP composites under inert atmosphere.

Flexural properties for UD composites with longitudinal disposition of the fibres were evaluated by 3 point bending tests on a universal testing machine (Instron 4426), following the ASTM D790M (see Fig. 4). The Young's modulus was evaluated from the slope of the stress-strain curve between 0.3 and 0.5% of flexural strain.

Fig. 4. 3PBT for bamboo fibre-PP composites (with fibres in longitudinal direction).

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Thermal degradation in single fibres

TGA analysis for single bamboo fibres in different environments, (air and argon) is shown in Fig. 5. A general mass loss delay is observed when the fibre is treated under inert atmosphere.

Fig. 5. TGA analysis for single bamboo fibres under Different environments (air and inert Argon).

Thermal degradation in natural fibres is a complex process and mainly depends on the structure and the chemical composition of the natural fibre. In Fig. 5, it is observed that the first drop in mass loss is due to the moisture evaporation, generally at temperatures below 100 °C.

At temperatures between 100 °C and 250 °C, some of the changes in physical properties of the fibers can be explained in terms of alterations in either physical or chemical structures such as depolymerization, hydrolysis, dehydration, decarboxylation and recrystallization. Besides this, the formation of free radicals has been noticed [8]. They can contribute to the formation of hydroperoxide groups, responsible to a large extent for the depolymerization of cellulose (by bond scission).

Besides depolymerization, a variety of oxidation and decomposition reactions take place, leading to the formation of carbonyl, carboxyl, lactone, and aldehyde functional groups [9]. All these reactions, specially the oxidative degradation of cellulose, take place primarily in the amorphous region of the cellulose [4], giving a drastic decrease in molecular weight and subsequent mechanical degradation. It has been found that pure hemicellulose starts its decomposition between 220 and 315 °C, with a maximum mass loss rate (0.95 wt.%/°C) at 268 °C

[10]. For bamboo fibres, hemicellulose degradation was found to take place at 275 °C in air, and at 288 °C when treated in inert environment (see Fig. 5).

At higher temperatures, the cellulose thermal degradation observed in the TGA analysis for the bamboo fibres (310 °C), is mainly caused by the destruction of hydrogen bridges, the loss of water, glass transitions, changes in crystallinity, and some processes mentioned before (i.e., the formation of free radicals, carbonyl groups, and carboxyl groups) but at a larger scale (especially in air) [9]. The cellulose decomposition under inert environment is shifted around 20 °C.

The lignin degradation is only visible for the fibres treated in air at around 444 °C. Pure lignin was found to be the most difficult one to decompose, doing it slowly over the whole temperature range from ambient to 900 °C [10]. Generally, the contribution of hemicellulose and cellulose to the thermal degradation is of much higher importance than that of lignin [11].

3.1.2 Thermally treated single fibres

In order to have a better understanding of the mechanical behaviour of the composite, tensile tests for single bamboo fibres (in air environment) were analyzed after thermal treatment at different temperature-time couples, see Table 2. The results are shown in Figs. 6 and 7.

Bamboo fibre strength is evidently affected depending of the temperature-time couples. This dependency has been also observed by Wielage *et al* [4], where higher temperatures and longer exposure times result in higher decreases of the mechanical properties. Also, it has been found that low temperatures (150 °C) and longer exposure times (up to 4h) reduced significantly the tenacity of ramie fibers [8]. A considerable drop in properties due to thermal treatment is not observed for the stiffness of the bamboo fibres, which remains in between 36 and 45 GPa for all conditions and quite stable for low temperature thermal treatments, see Fig. 7.

Fig. 6. Fibre strength after thermal treatment (in air) at different temperature-time couples.

Fig. 7. Young's modulus for the fibres after thermal treatment (in air) at different temperature-time couples.

A clear positive effect on fibre strength is observed when the thermal treatment is carried out under inert atmosphere (Fig. 8). The strength is improved by 37 and 45% for treatments at 200 and 250 °C respectively. Fibre stiffness does not show significant difference when the fibres are treated under different environments (air and argon), see Fig. 9.

SEM micrographs were made of the fibre fracture surfaces. For untreated fibres, mainly three types of fracture were identified: (a) a straight crack right through the elementary fibres, (b) a crack proceeding along the primary layer that surrounds the elementary fibres and (c), a combination of the

two. There was not found a systematic frequency of the failure types. The stress-strain curve is linear until failure with a strain to failure of 1.7 ± 0.2 %.

For thermally treated fibres, especially up to 220 °C and exposure times higher than 50 minutes, a higher brittleness of the fibres is observed with a correspondent reduction in the strain to failure which drops significantly. The type of fracture for these fibres changed to a more “clean” fracture surface after tensile testing, see Fig. 10.

Fig. 8. Fibre strength of thermally treated fibres at 200 and 250 °C in air and argon environments.

Fig. 9. Young's modulus for the fibres thermally treated at 200 °C, under air and argon atmosphere.

Other studies have indicated that higher thermal resistance of flax [12], jute [13] and hemp [5] fibres is found, when treated under inert atmosphere, where the process of decomposition of cellulose occurs much quicker in air environment.

Fig. 10. SEM micrograph of a typical fibre fracture after thermal treatment, showing more brittle fracture.

3.2 Bamboo fibre-PP composites

The flexural strength of bamboo fibre-PP composites at different consolidation temperatures is shown in Fig. 11.

Fig. 11. Flexural strength for BFPC consolidated (in air) at different temperatures.

BFPC's manufactured at temperatures up to 200 °C, present a good behaviour in flexural strength. They exhibited higher flexural strain to failure (~2 %) in comparison composites manufactured at higher temperatures, but also show a continuous deformation without a clear fracture when tested in 3PBT.

The good thermal resistance for single fibres under the inert environment is effectively translated to the flexural strength of the composites. An improvement of 6 and 30% at 220 and 230 °C respectively was

reached in comparison with the composites produced in air. For the Young's modulus evaluated in this study, the results did not show conclusive results based on what was found for single fibres.

During production of natural fibre reinforced plastics, similar studies have revealed that short periods of exposure to high temperatures are allowed without a significant decrease of the properties of the fibre [14]. For instance, in flax fibre, the decrease in mechanical properties due to exposure times at 200 °C shorter than 4 min was not significant [8].

4. Conclusions

It was found that the use of inert atmosphere during the consolidation phase can be a well controlled process that can be easily adapted for the processing of natural fibres and thermoplastics. The results show that the inert atmosphere had a positive effect on the mechanical properties for individual bamboo fibres, especially in a temperature range between 220 and 250 °C with improvements of 37 and 45 % respectively. Flexural strength for bamboo fibre/ polypropylene composites consolidated under inert atmosphere, indicated a significant improvement (30%) of the flexural strength, especially for (relatively) high processing temperatures (230 °C).

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References

- [1] X. Londoño, G. Camayo, N. Riaño, and Y. López, "Characterization of the anatomy of *Guadua angustifolia* (Poaceae: Bambusoideae) culms," *J. Am. Bamboo Soc.*, vol. 16, pp. 18-31, 2002.
- [2] K. Okubo, T. Fujii, and Y. Yamamoto, "Development of bamboo-based polymer composites and their mechanical properties," *Composite. Part A: Appl Sci Manuf*, vol. 35, pp. 377-383, 2004.
- [3] L. Osorio, E. Trujillo, A. W. Van Vuure, and I. Verpoest, "Morphological aspects and mechanical properties of single bamboo fibers and flexural characterization of bamboo/ epoxy composites," *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, vol. 30, pp. 396-408, March 1, 2011 2010.
- [4] B. Wielage, T. Lampke, G. Marx, K. Nestler, and D. Starke, "Thermogravimetric and differential scanning calorimetric analysis of natural fibres and polypropylene," *Thermochimica Acta*, vol. 337, pp. 169-177, 1999.
- [5] B. Prasad and M. Sain, "Mechanical properties of thermally treated hemp fibers in inert atmosphere for potential composite reinforcement," *Materials Research Innovations*, vol. 7, pp. 231-238, 2003.
- [6] D. Tripathy, *Practical guide to polypropylene*. UK, 2002.
- [7] N. Defoirdt, S. Biswas, L. De Vrise, N. Tran, J. Van Acker, Q. Ahsan, L. Gorbatikh, A. W. Van Vuure, and I. Verpoest, "Assessment of the tensile properties of coir, bamboo and jute fibre," *Composite Part A: Appl Sci Manuf*, vol. 41, pp. 588-595, 2010.
- [8] J. Gassan and A. K. Bledzki, "Thermal degradation of flax and jute fibers," *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, vol. 82, pp. 1417-1422, 2001.
- [9] K. Van De Velde and P. Kiekens, "Thermal degradation of flax: The determination of kinetic parameters with thermogravimetric analysis," *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, vol. 83, pp. 2634-2643, 2002.
- [10] H. Yang, R. Yan, H. Chen, D. H. Lee, and C. Zheng, "Characteristics of hemicellulose, cellulose and lignin pyrolysis," *Fuel*, vol. 86, pp. 1781-1788, 2007.
- [11] A. Rachini, M. Le Troedec, C. Peyratout, and A. Smith, "Comparison of the thermal degradation

of natural, alkali-treated and silane-treated hemp fibers under air and an inert atmosphere," *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, vol. 112, pp. 226-234, 2009.

- [12] K. Van de Velde and E. Baetens, "Thermal and Mechanical Properties of Flax Fibres as Potential Composite Reinforcement," *Macromolecular Materials and Engineering*, vol. 286, pp. 342-349, 2001.
- [13] T. Doan, H. Brodowsky, and E. Mader, "Jute fibre/polypropylene composites II. Thermal, hydrothermal and dynamic mechanical behaviour," *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 67, pp. 2707-2714, 2007.
- [14] S. Ochi, H. Takagi, and R. Niki, "Mechanical properties of heated-treated natural fibers," in *High performance Structures and Composites*, C. Brebbia and W. De Wilde, Eds. Southampton: WIT press, 2002, pp. 117-123.